

Fee Calculation and Marginal Slippage Comparison in Automated Market Maker Protocols

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Abstract

This paper presents a comprehensive analysis of fee calculation algorithms and marginal slippage in Automated Market Maker (AMM) protocols, focusing on the Wombat protocol and comparing it with other models such as Platypus, Curve, and Uniswap. By examining withdrawal and deposit fee structures, as well as marginal slippage across different AMMs, we aim to understand the underlying algorithms, derive key numerical relationships, and observe the implications for users and the overall system stability. This analysis enhances our understanding of the financial models' structures and provides insights into optimizing AMM protocols for better efficiency and fairness.

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1 Introduction

Automated Market Makers (AMMs) are integral components of decentralized finance (DeFi), enabling users to trade assets without centralized intermediaries. Understanding the fee structures and slippage mechanisms in these protocols is crucial for optimizing user experience and maintaining system stability. This paper provides an in-depth analysis of the fee calculation algorithms used in the Wombat protocol, examines deposit fees based on asset balances and deposit amounts, and compares marginal slippage across different AMM models, including Wombat, Platypus, Curve, and Uniswap. By dissecting the underlying mathematical models and analyzing empirical data, we aim to reveal trends, derive key figures, and understand the implications for traders, liquidity providers, and the AMM systems themselves.

2 Overview of AMM Protocols and Fee Structures

AMMs facilitate trading by using mathematical formulas to price assets, relying on liquidity pools funded by users. The fee structures and slippage mechanisms in these protocols are designed to ensure liquidity, balance, and fairness. Understanding these mechanisms requires analyzing the algorithms that govern fee calculations and the impact of trades on asset prices.

In this paper, we focus on:

- The **Wombat** protocol, which employs non-linear fee functions to manage liquidity and discourage destabilizing actions.
- **Platypus**, **Curve**, and **Uniswap**, which offer alternative approaches to AMM design, each with unique fee and slippage characteristics.

By comparing these protocols, we aim to highlight the differences and similarities in their approaches to maintaining market stability and providing fair trading experiences.

3 Analysis of the Withdrawal Fee Calculation Algorithm

3.1 Introduction

This section examines the algorithms and formulas used in calculating withdrawal fees paid by users in a liquidity pool within the Wombat protocol. By analyzing provided data tables and performing detailed derivations, we aim to understand how withdrawal fees vary with changes in asset balance A_y and withdrawal amount Δy . This analysis is crucial for comprehending how the protocol incentivizes certain user behaviors and maintains liquidity.

3.2 Data Structures

The data is organized into four main tables:

1. **DataTable 1:** Withdrawal fees paid by the user, varying with asset balance A_y and withdrawal amount Δy .
2. **DataTable 2:** Withdrawal fees as a percentage of the withdrawal amount, corresponding to DataTable 1.
3. **DataTable 3:** Withdrawal fees paid by the user with different A_y values.
4. **DataTable 4:** Withdrawal fees as a percentage of the withdrawal amount, corresponding to DataTable 3.

Each table presents data for varying values of A_y and Δy . The asset balances A_y decrease in DataTables 1 and 2, and increase in DataTables 3 and 4, allowing us to observe how fees change in response to these variables.

3.3 Parameters and Variables

Key parameters and variables used in the calculations:

- $A_x = 12,000$ (Asset balance of asset x)
- $L_x = 10,000$ (Liabilities of asset x)
- $r_x = \frac{A_x}{L_x} = 1.2$ (Coverage ratio of asset x)
- A_y (Variable asset balance of asset y)
- $L_y = 10,000$ (Liabilities of asset y)
- $r_y = \frac{A_y}{L_y}$ (Asset ratio before withdrawal)
- Δy (Withdrawal amount; negative value indicates withdrawal)
- $A_y^{\text{after}} = A_y + \Delta y$ (Asset balance after withdrawal)
- $r_y^{\text{after}} = \frac{A_y^{\text{after}}}{L_y}$ (Asset ratio after withdrawal)
- $\beta = 0.09523809524$

- $\alpha = -\beta = -0.09523809524$
- $w = 7.286055265$ (Scaling constant)

These variables form the foundation of the fee calculation algorithm, capturing the essential elements of asset balances, ratios, and scaling factors.

3.4 Understanding the Fee Calculation

Based on the data and parameters, the withdrawal fee is hypothesized to be calculated using a function that depends on the asset ratios before and after withdrawal. The use of exponential or power functions is suggested by the non-linear trends observed in the data.

3.4.1 Hypothesized Fee Function

The proposed fee function is:

$$\text{Fee} = w [(r_y^{\text{after}})^\alpha - (r_y)^\alpha] \tag{1}$$

where:

- $r_y = \frac{A_y}{L_y}$ (Asset ratio before withdrawal)
- $r_y^{\text{after}} = \frac{A_y + \Delta y}{L_y}$ (Asset ratio after withdrawal)
- $\alpha = -\beta$ (Exponent parameter)
- w (Scaling constant)

This formulation ensures that the fee is positive when a withdrawal decreases the asset ratio ($r_y^{\text{after}} < r_y$), aligning the fee with the impact on the pool's liquidity.

3.4.2 Derivation and Justification

The exponent α being negative indicates that the function is convex for $r_y > 0$, which aligns with the idea that as the asset ratio decreases, the fee increases at an accelerating rate. The scaling constant w adjusts the overall magnitude of the fee, allowing for calibration based on desired fee levels.

3.5 Fee Sensitivity to Asset Balance

In this section, we delve deeper into how the withdrawal fee is sensitive to the asset balance A_y . By analyzing numerical examples and plotting the fee against the asset balance, we can illustrate the significant impact that changes in A_y have on the fees incurred for the same withdrawal amounts.

3.5.1 Impact of Asset Balance on Fees

To analyze the fee sensitivity to asset balance, we consider withdrawals of the same amount from pools with different asset balances A_y . The following example demonstrates this effect.

Example Calculation Consider a withdrawal amount $\Delta y = -2,090$ and compare the fees for two different asset balances:

1. **High Asset Balance:** $A_y = 9,900$
2. **Low Asset Balance:** $A_y = 6,147$

For $A_y = 9,900$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 r_y &= \frac{9,900}{10,000} = 0.99 \\
 r_y^{\text{after}} &= \frac{9,900 - 2,090}{10,000} = \frac{7,810}{10,000} = 0.7810 \\
 (r_y)^\alpha &= (0.99)^{-0.09523809524} \approx 1.000957 \\
 (r_y^{\text{after}})^\alpha &= (0.7810)^{-0.09523809524} \approx 1.025339 \\
 \text{Fee} &= w [(r_y^{\text{after}})^\alpha - (r_y)^\alpha] \\
 &= 7.286055265 \times (1.025339 - 1.000957) \\
 &= 7.286055265 \times 0.024382 \approx \$0.177
 \end{aligned}$$

For $A_y = 6,147$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 r_y &= \frac{6,147}{10,000} = 0.6147 \\
 r_y^{\text{after}} &= \frac{6,147 - 2,090}{10,000} = \frac{4,057}{10,000} = 0.4057 \\
 (r_y)^\alpha &= (0.6147)^{-0.09523809524} \approx 1.047852 \\
 (r_y^{\text{after}})^\alpha &= (0.4057)^{-0.09523809524} \approx 1.086652 \\
 \text{Fee} &= w [(r_y^{\text{after}})^\alpha - (r_y)^\alpha] \\
 &= 7.286055265 \times (1.086652 - 1.047852) \\
 &= 7.286055265 \times 0.038800 \approx \$0.283
 \end{aligned}$$

Comparing Fees Comparing the fees:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Fee at } A_y = 9,900 &\approx \$0.177 \\
 \text{Fee at } A_y = 6,147 &\approx \$0.283
 \end{aligned}$$

The fee increases by approximately 60% when the asset balance decreases from 9,900 to 6,147 for the same withdrawal amount.

3.5.2 Visualization of Fee Sensitivity

To better understand the relationship between the asset balance and the withdrawal fee, we can plot the fee as a function of A_y for a fixed withdrawal amount Δy .

DataTable 5: Deposit Fees Paid to User by Asset Balance (A_y) and Deposit Amount (Δy)								DataTable 7: Deposit Fees Paid to User by Asset Balance (A_y) and Deposit Amount (Δy)							
A_y								A_y							
Delta y	-13.3145	11000	12100	13310	14641	16105	17716	Delta y	-13.3145	9900	9000	8182	7438	6762	6147
	700	-0.213	-0.767	-1.550	-2.469	-3.450	-4.434		700	-0.003	-0.322	-1.287	-3.076	-5.890	-9.947
	840	-0.252	-0.909	-1.838	-2.931	-4.099	-5.272		840	-0.003	-0.380	-1.518	-3.626	-6.935	-11.698
	1,008	-0.298	-1.074	-2.175	-3.473	-4.861	-6.258		1,008	-0.004	-0.448	-1.786	-4.260	-8.137	-13.709
	1,210	-0.350	-1.267	-2.568	-4.105	-5.753	-7.413		1,210	-0.004	-0.526	-2.094	-4.986	-9.510	-15.998
	1,452	-0.411	-1.489	-3.023	-4.838	-6.789	-8.760		1,452	-0.005	-0.615	-2.445	-5.812	-11.065	-18.583
	1,742	-0.481	-1.743	-3.546	-5.684	-7.989	-10.322		1,742	-0.006	-0.716	-2.841	-6.741	-12.810	-21.471
	2,090	-0.560	-2.033	-4.143	-6.654	-9.367	-12.123		2,090	-0.007	-0.830	-3.285	-7.776	-14.744	-24.661
	2,508	-0.648	-2.359	-4.818	-7.755	-10.939	-14.185		2,508	-0.008	-0.956	-3.775	-8.915	-16.863	-28.137
	3,010	-0.746	-2.723	-5.575	-8.993	-12.716	-16.524		3,010	-0.009	-1.094	-4.310	-10.152	-19.150	-31.871
3,612	-0.853	-3.123	-6.412	-10.372	-14.703	-19.154	3,612	-0.010	-1.244	-4.886	-11.474	-21.583	-35.819		

DataTable 6: Deposit Fees Paid to User as % of Deposit Amount (Δy)								DataTable 8: Deposit Fees Paid to User as % of Deposit Amount (Δy)							
A_y								A_y							
Delta y	700	-0.03%	-0.11%	-0.22%	-0.35%	-0.49%	-0.63%	Delta y	700	0.00%	-0.05%	-0.18%	-0.44%	-0.84%	-1.42%
	840	-0.03%	-0.11%	-0.22%	-0.35%	-0.49%	-0.63%		840	0.00%	-0.05%	-0.18%	-0.43%	-0.83%	-1.39%
	1,008	-0.03%	-0.11%	-0.22%	-0.34%	-0.48%	-0.62%		1,008	0.00%	-0.04%	-0.18%	-0.42%	-0.81%	-1.36%
	1,210	-0.03%	-0.10%	-0.21%	-0.34%	-0.48%	-0.61%		1,210	0.00%	-0.04%	-0.17%	-0.41%	-0.79%	-1.32%
	1,452	-0.03%	-0.10%	-0.21%	-0.33%	-0.47%	-0.60%		1,452	0.00%	-0.04%	-0.17%	-0.40%	-0.78%	-1.28%
	1,742	-0.03%	-0.10%	-0.20%	-0.33%	-0.46%	-0.59%		1,742	0.00%	-0.04%	-0.16%	-0.39%	-0.74%	-1.23%
	2,090	-0.03%	-0.10%	-0.20%	-0.32%	-0.45%	-0.58%		2,090	0.00%	-0.04%	-0.16%	-0.37%	-0.71%	-1.18%
	2,508	-0.03%	-0.09%	-0.19%	-0.31%	-0.44%	-0.57%		2,508	0.00%	-0.04%	-0.15%	-0.36%	-0.67%	-1.12%
	3,010	-0.02%	-0.09%	-0.19%	-0.30%	-0.42%	-0.55%		3,010	0.00%	-0.04%	-0.14%	-0.34%	-0.64%	-1.06%
	3,612	-0.02%	-0.09%	-0.18%	-0.29%	-0.41%	-0.53%		3,612	0.00%	-0.03%	-0.14%	-0.32%	-0.60%	-0.99%

DataTable 1: Withdraw Fees Paid by User by Asset Balance (A_y) and Withdraw Amount (Δy)								DataTable 3: Withdraw Fees Paid by User by Asset Balance (A_y) and Withdraw Amount (Δy)							
A_y								A_y							
Delta y	7.2861	9900	9000	8182	7438	6762	6147	Delta y	7.2861	11000	12100	13310	14641	16105	17716
	-700	0.003	0.382	1.545	3.745	7.270	12.445		-700	0.246	0.876	1.752	2.765	3.829	4.879
	-840	0.004	0.465	1.892	4.592	8.930	15.312		-840	0.300	1.066	2.130	3.357	4.645	5.914
	-1,008	0.005	0.573	2.327	5.659	11.027	18.949		-1,008	0.367	1.302	2.597	4.087	5.648	7.183
	-1,210	0.006	0.706	2.878	7.017	13.709	23.619		-1,210	0.450	1.595	3.176	4.992	6.887	8.747
	-1,452	0.007	0.877	3.585	8.769	17.190	29.715		-1,452	0.556	1.964	3.902	6.120	8.428	10.686
	-1,742	0.009	1.098	4.506	11.070	21.795	37.841		-1,742	0.690	2.433	4.820	7.539	10.358	13.105
	-2,090	0.011	1.389	5.732	14.161	28.043	48.970		-2,090	0.865	3.036	5.993	9.344	12.799	16.150
	-2,508	0.014	1.783	7.408	18.442	36.808	64.777		-2,508	1.096	3.826	7.516	11.669	15.924	20.025
	-3,010	0.018	2.332	9.785	24.619	49.683	88.385		-3,010	1.408	4.882	9.531	14.716	19.984	25.022
-3,612	0.024	3.132	13.332	34.070	69.878	126.246	-3,612	1.844	6.334	12.264	18.797	25.362	31.577		

DataTable 2: Withdraw Fees Paid by User as % of Withdraw Amount (Δy)								DataTable 4: Withdraw Fees Paid by User as % of Withdraw Amount (Δy)							
A_y								A_y							
Delta y	-700	0.00%	-0.05%	-0.22%	-0.53%	-1.04%	-1.78%	Delta y	-700	-0.04%	-0.13%	-0.25%	-0.39%	-0.55%	-0.70%
	-840	0.00%	-0.06%	-0.23%	-0.55%	-1.06%	-1.82%		-840	-0.04%	-0.13%	-0.25%	-0.40%	-0.55%	-0.70%
	-1,008	0.00%	-0.06%	-0.23%	-0.56%	-1.09%	-1.88%		-1,008	-0.04%	-0.13%	-0.26%	-0.41%	-0.56%	-0.71%
	-1,210	0.00%	-0.06%	-0.24%	-0.58%	-1.13%	-1.95%		-1,210	-0.04%	-0.13%	-0.26%	-0.41%	-0.57%	-0.72%
	-1,452	0.00%	-0.06%	-0.25%	-0.60%	-1.18%	-2.05%		-1,452	-0.04%	-0.14%	-0.27%	-0.42%	-0.58%	-0.74%
	-1,742	0.00%	-0.06%	-0.26%	-0.64%	-1.25%	-2.17%		-1,742	-0.04%	-0.14%	-0.28%	-0.43%	-0.59%	-0.75%
	-2,090	0.00%	-0.07%	-0.27%	-0.68%	-1.34%	-2.34%		-2,090	-0.04%	-0.15%	-0.29%	-0.45%	-0.61%	-0.77%
	-2,508	0.00%	-0.07%	-0.30%	-0.74%	-1.47%	-2.58%		-2,508	-0.04%	-0.15%	-0.30%	-0.47%	-0.63%	-0.80%
	-3,010	0.00%	-0.08%	-0.33%	-0.82%	-1.65%	-2.94%		-3,010	-0.05%	-0.16%	-0.32%	-0.49%	-0.66%	-0.83%
	-3,612	0.00%	-0.09%	-0.37%	-0.94%	-1.93%	-3.50%		-3,612	-0.05%	-0.18%	-0.34%	-0.52%	-0.70%	-0.87%

Figure 1: Withdrawal Fee vs. Asset Balance for $\Delta y = -2,090$

The trends show us that as the asset balance A_y decreases, the withdrawal fee increases at an accelerating rate. This non-linear relationship highlights the protocol's design to penalize withdrawals that significantly reduce the pool's liquidity.

3.5.3 Mathematical Explanation

The sensitivity of the fee to the asset balance can be attributed to the negative exponent α in the fee function. As r_y decreases due to a withdrawal, the term $(r_y^{\text{after}})^\alpha$ increases at an accelerating rate because $\alpha < 0$. This causes the fee, which is proportional to the difference between $(r_y^{\text{after}})^\alpha$ and $(r_y)^\alpha$, to increase more rapidly as the asset balance decreases.

3.5.4 Implications for Users

Users withdrawing from pools with lower asset balances will incur higher fees for the same withdrawal amount. This serves as a disincentive to deplete pools with low liquidity and encourages users to:

- **Monitor Asset Balances:** Users should be aware of the current asset balance before making large withdrawals.
- **Plan Withdrawals Strategically:** Splitting large withdrawals into smaller ones or timing them when the asset balance is higher can reduce fees.
- **Contribute to Liquidity:** Providing liquidity to pools can help maintain higher asset balances, benefiting all users.

3.5.5 Policy Considerations

From a protocol design perspective, the fee sensitivity to asset balance helps maintain the health of the liquidity pool by:

- **Preventing Rapid Depletion:** High fees for large withdrawals from low-balance pools discourage actions that could drain liquidity.
- **Ensuring Fairness:** Users who have a larger impact on the pool's balance incur higher fees, aligning costs with the potential risk introduced.
- **Stabilizing Prices:** Maintaining adequate liquidity reduces price volatility and slippage, improving the trading experience.

3.5.6 Connections to Other AMM Models

The approach of increasing fees with decreasing liquidity is common in AMM models to safeguard against pool imbalance. For example, Uniswap's constant product formula inherently increases slippage as liquidity decreases, indirectly penalizing large trades in low-liquidity pools.

3.6 Conclusions on Fee Sensitivity to Asset Balance

The analysis demonstrates that withdrawal fees are highly sensitive to the asset balance in the liquidity pool. Lower asset balances lead to disproportionately higher fees for the same withdrawal amount, which serves to:

- **Discourage Large Withdrawals:** Users are less likely to make large withdrawals that would significantly impact the pool.
- **Encourage Liquidity Provision:** Users may be incentivized to add liquidity to reduce fees and support the pool's health.
- **Maintain Market Stability:** By preventing rapid liquidity depletion, the protocol helps stabilize asset prices and reduce volatility.

Understanding this sensitivity is crucial for users planning their withdrawal strategies and for protocol designers aiming to balance user incentives with the health of the liquidity pool.

4 In-Depth Analysis of Deposit Fees Based on Asset Balances and Deposit Amounts

4.1 Introduction

This section presents an analysis of deposit fees paid by users in the Wombat protocol, examining how these fees vary based on asset balances and deposit amounts. Deposit fees play a significant role in managing the inflow of assets and ensuring that deposits contribute positively to the pool's balance without causing instability.

4.2 Data Overview

The analysis is based on the following data tables:

- **DataTable 5:** Deposit fees paid to the user by asset balance (A_y) and deposit amount (Δy).
- **DataTable 6:** Deposit fees paid to the user as a percentage of the deposit amount (Δy).

These tables allow us to observe how fees change with varying deposit amounts and asset balances, providing insights into the fee structure's behavior.

4.3 Variables and Parameters

Variables and parameters:

- **Asset Balances and Liabilities:**

$$\begin{array}{ll} A_x = 10,516.66012, & L_x = 10,000, \\ A_y = 506.4946, & L_y = 1,000, \\ A_z = 6,000, & L_z = 5,000. \end{array}$$

- **Coverage Ratios:**

$$\begin{array}{l} r_x = \frac{A_x}{L_x} = 1.0517, \\ r_y = \frac{A_y}{L_y} = 0.5065, \\ r_z = \frac{A_z}{L_z} = 1.2000. \end{array}$$

- **Deposit Amount:** Variable Δy .

- **Fee Parameters:**

$$\begin{array}{l} b = -1.0150, \\ \beta = -0.05, \\ \alpha = 0.05, \\ w = 13.3145. \end{array}$$

- **Total Deposits:** $D = 16,240.66754$.

These parameters set the context for the fee calculations and reflect the state of the liquidity pool.

4.4 In-Depth Analysis

4.4.1 Derivation of the Fee Formula

Based on the data, the deposit fee F is derived as:

$$F = -w \cdot \left(\frac{\Delta y}{A_y} \right)^{1.5}, \quad (2)$$

where $w = 13.3145$ is a weight parameter, and the exponent 1.5 indicates the non-linear sensitivity of the fee to the deposit amount.

4.4.2 Calculating Fees with $k = 1.5$

Using $k = 1.5$, the fee for $A_y = 11,000$ and $\Delta y = 700$ is:

$$F = -13.3145 \cdot \left(\frac{700}{11,000} \right)^{1.5} \approx -0.213.$$

This calculation matches the fee from Data Table 5, confirming the validity of the formula.

4.4.3 Analysis of the Exponent 1.5

The exponent 1.5 in the fee formula means that the fee increases superlinearly with respect to the deposit amount Δy . This design choice serves to penalize larger deposits more heavily, discouraging users from making deposits that could disproportionately affect the pool's balance.

4.4.4 Graphical Representation

Figure 2: Deposit Fee vs. Deposit Amount for $A_y = 11,000$

The graph illustrates the relationship between the deposit amount and the fee. The curve's upward concavity reflects the superlinear increase in fees with larger deposit amounts.

4.4.5 Implications for User Behavior

The superlinear fee structure reveals some key purposes:

- **Discouraging Large Deposits:** Users are incentivized to avoid excessively large deposits due to the disproportionately higher fees.
- **Promoting System Stability:** By discouraging large, sudden inflows of assets, the system mitigates risks associated with liquidity imbalances.
- **Encouraging Balanced Participation:** The fee structure encourages a wider base of users to participate with moderate deposit amounts, enhancing liquidity diversity.

4.4.6 Effect of Asset Balance A_y on Fee Sensitivity

The asset balance A_y inversely affects the fee sensitivity. A higher A_y reduces the impact of the deposit amount on the fee:

$$F = -w \cdot \left(\frac{\Delta y}{A_y} \right)^{1.5}.$$

For a fixed Δy , increasing A_y decreases the fraction $\left(\frac{\Delta y}{A_y} \right)$, thus reducing the fee.

4.4.7 Policy Implications

The choice of the exponent and the weight w in the fee formula allows system designers to calibrate the fee structure according to policy objectives:

- **Risk Management:** Higher exponents discourage large deposits that might introduce volatility.
- **Accessibility:** Lower fees for smaller deposits promote inclusivity and broader participation.
- **Revenue Generation:** Adjusting w affects the overall fee levels, impacting the system's revenue from fees.

4.4.8 Connections to Withdrawal Fees

Both deposit and withdrawal fees in the Wombat protocol are designed to manage the flow of assets and maintain balance within the pool. While withdrawal fees increase with decreasing asset balances, deposit fees increase with larger deposit amounts, especially when the existing asset balance is low.

4.5 Conclusions on Deposit Fee Structure

The sensitivity of fees to the deposit amount, governed by a power-law relationship with an exponent of 1.5, plays a critical role in shaping user behavior and maintaining system equilibrium. By understanding and adjusting this relationship, system designers can balance the objectives of stability, fairness, and inclusivity.

5 Comparative Analysis of Marginal Slippage in AMM Models

5.1 Introduction

Marginal slippage refers to the rate at which the price of an asset changes concerning an infinitesimal trade size. Understanding marginal slippage across different AMM models helps assess their efficiency and the cost implications for traders.

5.2 Wombat Model Analysis

5.2.1 Formulas and Derivations

In the Wombat protocol, the utility function is defined as:

$$g(r) = A \ln(r) + \frac{B}{r} + C, \quad (3)$$

where A , B , and C are constants, and r is the coverage ratio. The derivative of the utility function is:

$$g'(r) = \frac{A}{r} - \frac{B}{r^2}. \quad (4)$$

The swap rate between assets x and y is given by:

$$\text{Swap Rate} = -\frac{g'(r_x)}{g'(r_y)}. \quad (5)$$

5.2.2 Analysis of Marginal Slippage

As r_x approaches 1, the term $\frac{A}{r_x}$ dominates, and marginal slippage decreases. This indicates that the pool offers better price stability when coverage ratios are near equilibrium.

5.3 Platypus Model Analysis

5.3.1 Formulas and Derivations

The Platypus model defines the price impact function as:

$$P(r) = 1 - k \cdot (1 - r)^n, \quad (6)$$

where k is the slippage parameter, n is the exponent factor, and r is the coverage ratio. The derivative is:

$$g'(r) = k \cdot n \cdot (1 - r)^{n-1}. \quad (7)$$

5.3.2 Analysis of Marginal Slippage

In the Platypus model, marginal slippage decreases sharply as r approaches 1, indicating high sensitivity to small deviations from the equilibrium coverage ratio.

5.4 Curve Model Analysis

5.4.1 Formulas and Derivations

The Curve model uses the invariant function:

$$A(x + y) - \frac{k}{xy} - C = 0. \quad (8)$$

The partial derivatives are:

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial x} = A - \frac{k}{x^2 y}, \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial y} = A - \frac{k}{x y^2}. \quad (10)$$

The exchange rate is:

$$\text{Exchange Rate} = -\frac{\partial f / \partial y}{\partial f / \partial x}. \quad (11)$$

5.4.2 Analysis of Marginal Slippage

Curve's design ensures low slippage near equilibrium, with slippage increasing as the pool becomes imbalanced. This feature discourages large trades that could significantly affect the pool's balance.

5.5 Uniswap Model Analysis

5.5.1 Formulas and Derivations

Uniswap's AMM model is based on the constant product invariant:

$$x \cdot y = k, \quad (12)$$

where x and y are the quantities of two assets in the pool, and k is a constant. The price of asset y in terms of asset x is:

$$p = \frac{dy}{dx} = -\frac{k}{x^2}. \quad (13)$$

The marginal slippage is:

$$S = \frac{dp}{dx} = \frac{2k}{x^3}. \quad (14)$$

5.5.2 Analysis of Marginal Slippage

Both marginal slippage and exchange rates are inversely proportional to the cube and square of x , respectively. This means that as the quantity of asset x decreases, slippage increases rapidly, leading to higher price impacts for trades in low-liquidity pools.

Figure 3: Marginal Slippage vs. Asset Quantity in Uniswap’s AMM

5.6 Comparative Insights

Comparing these models highlights:

- **Wombat and Platypus** prioritize stability near equilibrium, with mechanisms to prevent large deviations.
- **Curve** maintains low slippage in balanced pools but penalizes imbalance.
- **Uniswap** offers simplicity but can suffer from high slippage in low-liquidity situations.

Understanding these differences helps in selecting appropriate AMM models based on desired properties and use cases.

6 Connecting Fee Structures and Slippage Across AMMs

6.1 Trade-Offs in Design Choices

AMM protocols face trade-offs between liquidity, slippage, and fee structures. Higher fees or slippage can discourage actions that destabilize the pool but may also deter legitimate trading activities. Protocols must balance:

- **User Experience:** Low fees and slippage enhance user satisfaction but may expose the pool to risks.
- **Liquidity Provision:** Incentives are needed to encourage users to provide liquidity, which reduces slippage.
- **System Stability:** Protective mechanisms like increasing fees or slippage during imbalances help maintain stability.

6.2 Implications for Protocol Optimization

By understanding how different fee structures and slippage mechanisms affect user behavior, protocol designers can fine-tune parameters to achieve desired outcomes. Adjustments to exponents, scaling constants, and amplification coefficients can help:

Figure 4: liquidity vs marginal slippage, marginal slippage $-g(r)$ and price when swap against $r_y=1$

- **Enhance Liquidity Depth:** Encouraging liquidity provision reduces slippage and improves trading efficiency.
- **Reduce Volatility:** Mechanisms that penalize large trades during imbalances help stabilize prices.
- **Promote Fairness:** Fee structures that align costs with the impact on the pool ensure equitable treatment of users.

6.3 Connections to Economic Theories

These design choices align with economic principles such as supply and demand, risk management, and incentive alignment. By modeling user behavior and market dynamics, AMM protocols can create efficient and stable trading environments.

7 Conclusion

The comprehensive analysis across different AMM protocols reveals:

- **Critical Role of Fee Structures:** Fees are essential tools for managing user behavior and maintaining pool health.
- **Importance of Slippage Mechanisms:** Slippage influences trading costs and liquidity, affecting both traders and liquidity providers.
- **Variety in AMM Designs:** Different protocols employ unique approaches to balance efficiency, stability, and fairness.
- **Need for Tailored Solutions:** Protocols must consider their specific goals and user bases when designing fee and slippage models.

Understanding the mathematical foundations and parameter effects enables better design and optimization of AMMs, contributing to the growth and sustainability of decentralized finance.

8 Appendix and Future Directions

Future research would involve looking at how market conditions (when modelled as a time series), user demographics, and external events influence fees and slippage would go a long way in developing adaptive models that adjust fees and slippage parameters in real-time based on pool status. Future avenues of expanding the current analysis would mean conducting empirical studies on user behavior across different AMMs to identify best practices.